

**Session 3A:Data-driven and physics-based machine learning
methods for forecasting and knowledge discovery of subsurface hydrology
Wednesday, October 02, 2024
3:40 pm – 4:00 pm**

Hybrid data-driven and physics-based modeling of seawater intrusion in coastal aquifers

**Ming Cheng¹, Valentina Ciriello¹
Vittorio Di Federico^{1*}**

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

*(1) Dipartimento di Ingegneria Civile, Chimica, Ambientale e dei Materiali, Università di Bologna, Bologna, Italy
email: vittorio.difederico@unibo.it

The EU faces unprecedented environmental challenges of groundwater security under the impact of **climate and global change** (CC and GC).

The EU's water-dependent sectors generate **3.4 trillion€/year**, 26% of the EU's annual gross value added, and employ around **44 million** people.

MAR2PROTECT DEMO SITES

MAR2PROTECT is a 4-year project (2022-2026) under EU Horizon2022 aimed to — Preventing groundwater contamination and protecting its quality against harmful impacts of global and climate change

TYPE OF RESULT > M-AI-R PLATFORM

- DSS-MAR is a comprehensive simulation platform encompassing physical simulation, data-driven prediction, risk assessment, and decision-making. DRONE seeks to anticipate seawater intrusion using data-driven methods.

Novel Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) System

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLOBAL CHANGE

Rainfalls, floods, stormwater

Drought

Temperature Sea increase

Migration

Human activities

Industry

Agriculture

Reclaimed WW

WWTP

Estuaries

Rivers

Sea

Salt Intrusion

POLLUTANTS

N/P, pharmaceuticals, PFAS,
microplastics, pesticides

Aquifer
recharge

MAR – Managed Aquifer Recharge – natural barrier buffer capacity

GROUNDWATER

Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) is the most powerful tool to curb salinity intrusion and to prevent other types of GW contamination by injecting freshwater.

Challenges:

- Decision support tools for MAR in GC and CC scenarios
- Valid model-based MAR design tools
- Optimal control system for MAR

Managed Aquifer Recharge System

- **DRONE** : This Data-Driven Modeling tool will use nonstationary time series to forecast aquifer response to uncertain climate change impacts on groundwater and to support decision making for MAR system.

- The coastal phreatic aquifer of Emilia Romagna Region (Ravenna lies in the middle) is primarily located within the littoral sand and locally in the shallow marine wedge deposits.
- 25 piezometers sensor are deployed along the coastal line, the sensor provide as feedback the temperature and electrical conductivity data monthly and water quality data twice a year.
- Climate data and geological properties are collected for physical modeling and statistical analysis.

Single Well Prediction Model

$$u_i(\mathbf{x}) = \mu_i(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon_i(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} = (t, \mathbf{z}) \quad t: \text{time} \quad \mathbf{z}: \text{depth}$$

$\mu_i(\mathbf{x})$: Analytical or Numerical Model

$\epsilon_i(\mathbf{x}) \sim GP(0, k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}'))$ ϵ_i : Non-stationary Gaussian Process k : kernel function

Given time t

Integrate in to a general map

General Map Prediction Model

$$U(\mathbf{X}) = \Phi(\mathbf{X}) + \epsilon_g(\mathbf{X}) \quad \mathbf{X} = (X, Y, Z): \text{location on GIS map}$$

$\Phi(\mathbf{X})$: Physical Model or Statistic Model

$\epsilon_g \sim GP(0, K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}'))$: Non-stationary GP on GIS map

Groundwater flow equation

$$\nabla \cdot \left[\rho \frac{\beta_f}{\beta} \gamma_f (\nabla h + \frac{\rho - \rho_f}{\rho_f}) \nabla H_z \right] = \rho S_f \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \varphi \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial C} \frac{\partial C}{\partial t}$$

ρ :density of saline groundwater

ρ_f :density of fresh groundwater

β :dynamic viscosity of saline groundwater

β_f :dynamic viscosity of fresh groundwater

S_f :specific storage of fresh groundwater

φ : porosity

C :the concentration of salts in groundwater

γ_f :hydraulic conductivity

h :freshwater head

H_z :elevation head

For single well, we can use steady-state transport equation for approximation

$$\gamma_f \nabla h \cdot \nabla C + \gamma_f \frac{C}{C_s} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} + \varphi d \nabla^2 C = 0 \quad d : \text{diffusion coefficients} \quad C_s : \text{salt concentration in seawater}$$

We have analytical solution with Green function

! Different physical models can be incorporated into our framework. Here is an application.

Non-stationary kernel on space and time [for single-well data]

Gibbs kernel function on $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{z})$ t: time z: depth r: positive defined function

$$k_{Gibbs}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \theta_1 \prod_{i=1}^2 \left\{ \frac{2r_i(\mathbf{x}_i; \theta)r_i(\mathbf{x}'_i; \theta)}{r_i(\mathbf{x}_i; \theta)^2 + r_i(\mathbf{x}'_i; \theta)^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}'_j)^2}{r_j(\mathbf{x}_j; \theta)^2 + r_j(\mathbf{x}'_j; \theta)^2}\right)$$

Optimize hyperparameters θ by marginal likelihood function, D_i : Dataset for location i

$$\log p(u_i | D_i) = -u_i^T K_i^{-1} u_i - \frac{1}{2} \log(|K_i|) - \frac{n}{2} \log 2\pi$$

K_i is the covariance matrix at location i and n is the number of samples in training set

Gaussian kernel function on GIS map [for multiple wells]

Optimize linear coefficient v_i and relative length l of Non-stationary Gaussian kernel function,

$$G(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_i v_i \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_i\|_{GIS}^2}{l^2}\right) \quad K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}') = \frac{2|G(\mathbf{X})|^{\frac{1}{4}}|G(\mathbf{X}')|^{\frac{1}{4}}}{|G(\mathbf{X})+G(\mathbf{X}')|^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}'\|_{GIS}^2}{l^2}\right)$$

\mathbf{X}_i is the location of single well

Elciola

Mesola

Bosco Mesola

Vaccolino

Pinarella

Cesenatico

$$\text{Salinity} \approx 10f(\text{Temperature})EC_{25^{\circ}C}$$

15, Jan, 2023

15, Jun, 2023

15, Dec, 2023

Total Organic Carbon(TOC)

21, Oct, 2020

18, May, 2021

16, Feb, 2022

Ammonium ion

21, Oct, 2020

18, May, 2021

7, Feb, 2022

$$\text{Prediction} = \omega_1 \text{Physical Model(Seawater Intrusion and MAR)} + \omega_2 \text{Model Error(Pure Data-Driven Model)}$$

Given a MAR strategy to select the physical model

Select a place to apply MAR system and add its output into hybrid Data-driven model

Comparing the salinity level before and after MAR applied

- The non-stationary Gaussian Process model captures the characteristics of time series compared to stationary training (*Felisa et al., Data-driven models of groundwater salinization in coastal plains, J. Hydrol., 2015*).
- The hybrid structure allows for different physical models to be used as mean functions and incorporates machine learning within the GP or physical model to improve its performance.

We will address the overfitting issue and improve model predictions by incorporating geological data, climate information, and high-fidelity numerical simulations.

Next stage

Insert physical model of MAR into machine learning model to predict the effect on coastal aquifer

Thank you for your attention

Vittorio Di Federico

email: vittorio.difederico@unibo.it

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2022 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101082048. The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.